

Project-Based Educational Technology as a Method for Developing Social Activity of Students

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Abstract: Social activity and socialization of youth play an important role in society. Especially for female students, socialization is of great importance in strengthening their position in society, personal and professional development. In this article we will study the meaning, features and conditions of using project-based educational technologies in the socialization of female students and their role in increasing their social activity.

Keywords: project-based educational technology, female students, social activity, development.

Introduction: The sustainable development of society depends on the social activity of every conscious citizen in it, and the activation of young people is one of the most urgent issues. Social activity helps to strengthen the position of young people in society, their personal and professional development. Especially for female students, social activity is important in improving their knowledge and skills, and in their active participation in social and economic life. A number of scientists have contributed to the development of the problem of social activity, including scientists from our republic N. Egamberdiyeva, Q.Q. Quronboev, I. Ergashev, M. Rakhmonova, H. Hamzayev, Kh. Tojiboyeva, M. Makhmudova, Z. Shaumarova, N. Nurmatova, and scientists from foreign countries I. Kolesov, A.V. Ivanov, S. Kerkis, D. Reynolds Stephanie, Abu-Ghaida, etc.

Pedagogical scientist Q.Q.Kuronbaev, in his research, attaches great importance to the development of social activity of students, emphasizing that a person is not a weak product of social relations and that a person cannot live outside of social relations and social existence. Young people, in particular, female students, develop and improve in the process of these social relations. All social activity and knowledge of female students are the result of the direct influence of the social environment.

Materials.

Social activity means the active participation of a person in society, his inclusion in social processes, social relations and public affairs. This concept includes activities such as understanding the social role of a person, feeling responsibility, striving to join public affairs. There are various forms of social activity, which include social relations, collective activities, participation in social organizations and various other activities.

To ensure social justice, the active participation of all members of society, including girls, is important. Involving female students in social activity helps to ensure justice and equality in society. Experts recommend the use of project technology as one of the effective methods for developing socially active citizenship competencies of female students. It is noted that the project method can not only expand the scope of the educational process and form various basic competencies, but also be one of the effective methods of working on the formation of social activity.

Project educational technology teaches students to think independently, solve problems, be creative and work in a team. With the help of this technology, students, along with deepening their professional

knowledge, also develop their social skills. As A. S. Zylko and K. S. Bazhin noted, "The most effective means of developing social activity is to involve students in project activities."

Research and methods.

Project educational technologies (PBL - Project-Based Learning) are a practical method of education that involves students in activities such as problem solving, independent research, and teamwork.

In Latin, the term "project" - projection means "thrown forward". A project is a perfect form, embodiment of an expected or assumed object, state, in some cases - a plan, goal. According to K.M. Kantor, a project is a manifestation of the creative activity of the human mind. The author attaches great importance to the fact that a project is a special form of consciousness that can build any labor process.

The process of creating a project is called designing. According to E.I. Isaev, designing is the driving mechanism of developmental education: "The subject of designing is the creation of conditions for the development of a continuous educational system, for the transition from one state to another."

Project educational technologies are a teaching method based on the implementation of numerous projects and practical work. This approach allows students to learn theoretical knowledge through real-life and practical tasks. The main elements of project-based educational technology:

1. Project selection and topic presentation:

- Implementation of projects on the selected topic.
- Project topics should be aimed at solving real problems.

2. Interdisciplinary approach:

- Using knowledge from several disciplines during the project implementation process strengthens the general knowledge and skills of students.

3. Group work:

- During the project work, students work together in groups.
- Develops teamwork skills and social competencies.

4. Practice and experience:

- Projects should be based on practical activities.
- Students learn to apply theoretical knowledge in real-life situations.

5. Presentation and assessment:

- After the project is completed, students present their work and are evaluated on the basis of it.
- Develops presentation skills and critical thinking.

Through team projects, students learn to work together, communicate with each other, and distribute tasks in a team. This helps to improve their social skills.

Results.

When using design technology to develop socially active citizenship competencies in female students, we need to pay special attention to the following:

- take into account the specifics of adolescence, gender, and the diversity of interests based on their studies in different educational areas;
- it is recommended to distribute tasks taking into account the capabilities of students;
- along with organizing group work, an individual approach is necessary in providing psychological and socio-pedagogical counseling to female students;

- taking into account the needs of students for independent thinking, it is necessary to give them the opportunity to gain social and professional experience.

Discussion.

In our opinion, the only correct criterion for involving students in a successful socially active citizenship position is to obtain results that meet the expectations of all stakeholders. In this regard, in the process of project activities, the need for students to achieve not only the full implementation of the project goals, but also personal results plays an important role, which helps to form a positive attitude towards the stage of acquiring socially active citizenship skills. We consider its formation and development in the university environment as a process and result of qualitative and quantitative changes in the implementation of conscious interaction of female students with the social environment in order to change themselves and society in accordance with the tasks of social development associated with growth. The success of the project depends on the implementation of these conditions, which is characterized not only by the quality of projects, but also by the growth of creativity and social activity of female students.

In conclusion, project educational technologies help to increase self-management, independence and responsibility of female students. They develop these skills by independently planning and implementing their own projects. It is through these educational technologies that female students develop social skills such as teamwork, joint problem solving, and collective decision-making. This ensures their active participation in society. Through the correct use of project educational technology, female students develop important social skills such as self-management, problem solving, and teamwork. As a result, their social activity and place in society are strengthened.

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